

Concentration Dependence of Sedimentation Coefficient of Cellulose Trinitrate

B. DAS and A. K. RAY

Department of Applied Chemistry,
Calcutta University.

Manuscript received 29 March 1977, accepted 3 June 1977

SEDIMENTATION coefficients of macromolecules usually exhibit a pronounced dependence on the concentration of the solution. Although many attempts have been made to elucidate the reasons for such dependence and its relation to the properties of the macromolecules, our knowledge in this regard is still inadequate.

Various corrections have been proposed to obviate this difficulty. Lauffer¹ in a study on tobacco mosaic virus found that values of $S\eta/\eta_0$ are constant within a fairly wide concentration range. From theoretical considerations also, it is expected that the macromolecules will behave in the same way. Jullander² has concluded that S_0 can be determined with reasonable accuracy for cellulose nitrates of molecular weight $1-2 \times 10^5$ by multiplying S with relative viscosity of the solution having 60% of the original concentration.

Burgers³ proposed that the value of sedimentation coefficient at infinite dilution can be determined by extrapolating the data obtained at finite concentrations according to the equation

$$S = \frac{S_0}{1+kc} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{or, } S = S_0(1 - kc) \quad (2)$$

where S_0 is the sedimentation coefficient at infinite dilution, S the sedimentation coefficient at concentration c , and k a constant.

Newman⁴ et al have employed the following relation for extrapolation of sedimentation coefficients to infinite dilution

$$S = S_0(1 + k_s c + k'_s c^2)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where k_s and k'_s are constants and c the concentration. This relation is essentially the same as the Burgers' equation except that it contains an additional term in concentration. The coefficients k_s and k'_s were readily determined graphically by a difference method according to the next relation which follows simply from equation (3)

$$\left(\frac{1}{S_2} - \frac{1}{S_1} \right) / (c_2 - c_1) = k_s + k'_s(c_2 + c_1) \quad (4)$$

the subscripts 1 and 2 refer to any pair of data. This relation was found to represent the data very accurately.

NOTES

Following this, S_0 can be evaluated graphically from plots of $\left(\frac{1}{S} - k'_s c^2 \right)$ vs. c .

The present investigation aims to examine the applicability of these extrapolation procedures for the determination of accurate S_0 values.

Experimental

Dry cellulose samples were treated with a mixture of phosphorous pentoxide and fuming nitric acid according to the method proposed by Alexander and Mitchell⁵. Cellulose trinitrate samples thus obtained were washed free of acid and thoroughly solvent exchanged with methanol and benzene, respectively. These were finally dried under vacuo. Sedimentation velocity experiments of the cellulose trinitrate samples in ethyl acetate and acetone were carried out in a Spinco model E analytical ultracentrifuge at a rotor speed of 44,770 rpm, using Schlieren optics. The boundary displacements were measured with a Comparator (Osaw, India) reading upto four decimals.

Relative viscosities at each concentration were determined using an Ubbelohde dilution viscometer at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Results and Discussions

Values of $S_{20,w}$ are plotted against concentration in curve (1) of fig. 1. Samples of cellulose trinitrates, both in ethyl acetate and acetone, show a pronounced dependence on concentration. Corrections for relative viscosity were applied to these sedimentation coefficients and as can be seen, it resulted in an overcorrection for

Fig. 1. Plot of $S_{20,w}$ vs. c & $\eta_r \times S_{20,w}$ vs. c for Cellulose trinitrate in Acetone.

TABLE-1. SEDIMENTATION COEFFICIENT AND RELATIVE VISCOSITY OF CELULOSE TRINITRATE IN ACETONE.

Concentration gms/dl.	$S_{20,w} \times 10^{13}$	$\eta_r = \eta/\eta_0$	$\frac{1}{S_{20,w}} - K'_{s,c} \times c^2$	$S_{20,w} \times C$	$S_{20,w} \times \eta_r$
0.2955	2.178	9.443	0.4614	0.6436	20.57
0.2396	2.392	6.200	0.4195	0.5732	14.84
0.1977	2.734	4.350	0.3668	0.5405	11.90
0.1508	3.054	2.886	0.3281	0.4606	8.81
0.1044	3.505	2.048	0.2856	0.3659	7.18

values at higher concentrations. However, at lower concentrations, the corrections were very low at the lower percentages of relative viscosities.

The Burgers' equation and the Newman-Loeb relation when applied to the present system, resulted in very good linear plots and the values obtained by extrapolation to infinite dilution were found to be in good agreement. The plots are shown in figs. (2) and (3).

Fig. 2 Plot of $S_{20,w}$ vs $S_{20,w} \times c$ for Cellulose trinitrate in acetone.

Fig. 3 Plot of $\left(\frac{1}{S} - K'_{s,c} c^2\right)$ vs c for Cellulose trinitrate in acetone.

TABLE-2. SEDIMENTATION COEFFICIENT AND RELATIVE VISCOSITY OF CELLULOSE TRINITRATE IN ETHYL ACETATE.

0.2180	2.178	9.642	0.4558	0.4749	21.00
0.1665	2.500	6.269	0.3981	0.4162	15.67
0.1396	2.756	4.737	0.3614	0.3847	13.05
0.1230	2.712	3.856	0.3676	0.3329	10.46
0.0786	3.251	2.327	0.3072	0.2555	7.56

The values of sedimentation coefficients obtained in ethyl acetate and acetone do not show a pronounced difference. It is expected that the sedimentation coefficient will depend on the viscosity of the medium, more resistance to the flow of the solute molecules will be offered in a medium in which the viscosity is higher. The data in tables 1 and 2 fulfil this expectation.

References

1. M. A. LAUFFER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1195.
2. I. JULLANDER, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1948, 3, 631.
3. J. M. BURGERS, *Proc. Acad. Sci., Amsterdam*, 1941, 44, 1045; 1942, 45, 126.
4. S. NEWMAN, L. LOEB and C. M. CONRAD, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1953, 10, 463.
5. W. J. ALEXANDER and R. L. MITCHELL, *Anal. Chem.*, 1949, 21, 1947.

Chemical Investigation of *Rumex dentatus* Linn

B. K. BHADORIA and R. K. GUPTA

Indian Grassland and Fodder Research Institute, Jhansi, U. P.

Manuscript received 3 January 1977, revised 4 April 1977, accepted 3 June 1977

RUMEX dentatus Linn. (Polygonaceae) commonly grows as an annual herb in Bundelkhand, gangetic plains and the sub-Himalayan tract upto 1000'. The plant is highly toxic to livestock causing 'diarrhoea and dermatitis¹⁻³'. No reference on its components is available in the literature, although, sister species³⁻⁴